

APPRAISAL OF THE INCLUSION OF BAMBOO AS A MAINSTREAM BUILDING CONSTRUCTION MATERIAL IN CURRICULUM OF ARCHITECTURE SCHOOLS IN INDIA.

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ABSTRACT

India is second largest producer of Bamboo in the world, in spite of this Bamboo has not been acknowledged well as a mainstream construction material in the country. One of many reasons may be the lack of awareness and competence of Architects in using Bamboo technology. Professional competency of architects depends much on curriculum and academic upbringing. This paper attempts to analyse the architecture curriculum to appraise the status of inclusion of Bamboo as a mainstream building construction material in curricula of Architecture Schools across India. Effort is made to quantify the importance of Bamboo in curriculum offered to students.

KEYWORDS

Bamboo; construction; mainstream; material; inclusion; architecture; curriculum; status; India

INTRODUCTION

India has the largest area (13.96 million hectares) under Bamboo cultivation and it is the second largest producer of Bamboo in the world after China. It has rich Bamboo diversity with 126 indigenous and 11 exotic species grown in many parts of the country (Department of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare, 2019). Properties of Bamboo from the strength, durability and sustainability point of view are well known and proven. Bamboo can become a potential sustainable alternative for non-sustainable mainstream building construction materials that are used abundantly in building construction activity. Building construction sector accounts for sizable CO₂ (United Nations Environment Programme, 2021) emission leading to greenhouse effect and global warming. Greater use of Bamboo as a construction material can lead to reduction in usage of concrete, steel and other non-sustainable building construction material and eventually reduce environmental impact of construction activity.

PRESENT SCENARIO

Bamboo is not used as a mainstream material in the construction of buildings in most of the semi-rural as well as urban areas of India. It is used mainly for scaffolding and temporary construction work. To enhance usage of Bamboo in construction a multipronged approach is required to be adopted. Firstly the Bamboo needs to be acknowledged as a mainstream construction material by the main stake holders. Currently it is being seen as an alternative material than the mainstream construction material. There can be many reasons for this status of Bamboo in construction sector. One of the reasons may be associated with an important stakeholders of building construction industry i.e. Architect (Development Alternatives, 2014). During professional education of an architect enough importance and training may not have been given leaving the budding architects disinterested and incompetent in the usage of Bamboo. The curriculum of architecture may lack in adequate contents and required integration of Bamboo technology at various stages leading to lack of awareness, interest and competence (Development Alternatives, 2014).

ARCHITECTURE EDUCATION

Currently India has 421 active architecture schools spread across the various states of the country that are imparting architecture education to students to graduate after five years of coursework and become eligible for professional registration required to practice Architecture. These schools offer Five year

B.Arch. (Bachelor of Architecture) professional degree course recognised by Council of Architecture, a statutory body constituted by government of India under the provisions of the Architects Act, 1972. The Council of Architecture is mandated to regulate the architecture education and profession in the country. The schools of architecture are either autonomous or affiliated to the universities and they have their own curriculum or the one recommended by the affiliating university. Some of the schools are government aided and some are self-financing type. The Council of Architecture has given a general guidance on the inclusion of mandatory or optional courses and delivery of coursework (Council of Architecture, 2020). Number of courses, credits assigned to each course, the course contents and the coursework to be completed by students actually varies from institution to institution as per the vision and mission of their organisation. This paper has attempted to analyse the curricula and the syllabi of the architecture programs of various schools and universities in an effort to quantify the importance of Bamboo as a construction material indicated in those curricula. More than 100 syllabi applicable to 352 schools have been studied and analysed to draw conclusions that give an adequate idea about the status of recognition of Bamboo as a mainstream material by architecture academia. The extent of availability of data is given in table1 (Council of Architecture India, 2021).

Table1: Architecture Schools, intake at 1st year and availability of syllabi from websites for study

1	Total number of schools offering B.Arch. degree programme in India	421 (Number)
2	Total number of syllabi used for study and analysis out of 421	355 (Number)
3	Percentage of syllabi available for study and analysis	83.61 (%)
4	Total intake at first year level (in 421 schools)	22984 (Number)
5	Students intake of schools (355) for which syllabi are available for study	19854 (Number)
6	Percentage of relevant students intake available for study	86.38 (%)

Architecture curriculum and courses

For the purpose of analysis of curriculum and courses offered by architecture schools under B.Arch. program, the authentic syllabi of architecture schools were downloaded from the websites of the individual autonomous schools and universities. The data collected for 355 schools is analysed and compiled in table 2. Comparative content analysis approach (Mayring, 2014) is followed for quantification of contents on study of Bamboo as a building material in each syllabus

Methodology of Analysis and quantification

To conduct analysis and evaluation of syllabi of B.Arch. program following steps were followed.

- a) First a key word search for “Bamboo” in the syllabi is carried out to identify the courses containing topics on Bamboo.
- b) Syllabi not having any course with keyword “Bamboo” is treated as having zero weightage (zero credit) for study of Bamboo.
- c) Number of Courses containing keyword “Bamboo” in the syllabi are identified and studied in detail.
- d) It is observed that the syllabus of each course (subject) generally has four to five modules. Thereby each module carried an approximate weightage of 25% (for syllabus having 4 modules) to 20% (for syllabus having 5 modules).
- e) Each module contains 3 to 10 topics. Weightage to topics as such ranges from 8% to 2%.
- f) By scrutinizing each module of the identified courses (as mentioned in point no. 4 above), a weightage in terms of percent is assigned to contents on “Bamboo” in syllabus of that course by comparing total contents against contents related to Bamboo.
- g) Weightage of contents on Bamboo in the course is converted into credits from the credit value of that course mentioned in the syllabus scheme.
- h) For example: A course has total 3 credits (as mentioned in syllabus scheme). The contents on “Bamboo” in that course get 25% weightage. The weightage converted to credit value is $3 \times 25\% = 0.75$ Credits for topic on “Bamboo”.

- i) By following same procedure, sum of credits assigned to topic on “Bamboo” was calculated for relevant courses of all the syllabi.
- j) Average credits assigned to topics on study of “Bamboo” in syllabi of 355 Schools are finally calculated.

Table2: Architecture Schools, intake at 1st year and availability of syllabi from websites for study

1	Average number of courses offered by 355 schools over five years	81.54
2	Maximum number of courses offered by any school/university over five years	137
3	Minimum number of courses offered by any school/university over five years	53
4	Total applicable course credits for B.Arch. program (average for 355 schools)	259.06
5	Average applicable course credits for one course (average for 352 schools)	3.18
6	Average Number of courses related to construction, materials and sustainability	11.01
7	Maximum number of courses offered by any school that contain topic on Bamboo	4
8	Average number of courses offered by schools containing topic on Bamboo	1.039
9	Average weightage attributed to the topic of Bamboo in one course (subject)	8.26%
10	Average credits assigned to topic of Bamboo considering total number of courses	0.30
11	Number of schools offering independent course solely on Bamboo	3 (0.84%)
12	Number of courses containing Bamboo topics in guidance document of COA (Council of Architecture, Statutory body of Ministry of Education, India)	0 (Zero)

Fig 1: School syllabi data on subjects having topic on Bamboo

The Coursework on Bamboo forming part of the syllabi of the subjects of various schools differs in topics and contents. It is observed that the following topics on Bamboo have appeared in the syllabi of subjects in the curriculum of various schools.

Bamboo in vernacular architecture

This topic is included in the elective subject “Vernacular Architecture” offered by few schools. The subject includes the study of vernacular architecture of ancient period (during Vedic period) with Bamboo

as one of the materials used for construction of the buildings of that time. Study aims at understanding the forms of building enclosure and techniques of construction adopted using Bamboo as a construction material in those examples.

Properties and Types of Bamboo

Study of physical and structural properties of Bamboo, durability of Bamboo against loading and environmental agents is included in some of the courses. Types of Bamboo species and their suitability for construction, length and diameter appropriate for construction is also studied in some cases.

Treatment and Preservation of Bamboo

Students are taught about common treatment methods and techniques of preservation used for increasing the durability of Bamboo against weather, insects and decay. They are also informed about storage and stacking of Bamboo in a safe manner.

Bamboo joinery and details

Exposure and understanding of various types of joints between Bamboo poles as per the requirement is given to students. Suitability of joints as per the purpose, hardware and fixtures used to achieve joints between Horizontal/inclined and vertical elements is also explained through drawings of the details of common types of joints.

Techniques of construction

Study of construction techniques used for constructing foundation for Bamboo columns. Constructing composite columns using number of Bamboo poles. Construction of walls and partitions using Bamboo at various locations and integration with other materials like stone or mud. Construction techniques for Bamboo roofing and flooring. Fabrication and details of doors and windows using Bamboo. Techniques of fabrication of trusses and girders using Bamboo for long spans and inclined roofs or roofs of other form.

Integration of Bamboo in design

In very few cases studio exercises are introduced to integrate Bamboo in design in a conventional as well as in unconventional manner. Objective is to make students try creative forms for small space enclosures.

Bamboo for making models

Students are made to use Bamboo for making scaled models to explore possible forms for enclosing spaces and for making scale models of building elements.

Study and analysis revealed that most of the syllabi had only one topic and few had between 2 & 4 from the above mentioned topics on Bamboo. Very few schools have syllabi containing the entire set of above mentioned topics spread over three or four courses offered at various levels of study. More than 25 courses containing topic of Bamboo for construction have been analysed. These courses containing topics of study on Bamboo have been broadly categorised as follows

Category A: History of Architecture/Vernacular Architecture/Traditional Architecture

Category B: Building Materials/Building Construction and Materials/Construction technology

Category C: Non-conventional materials & techniques/Appropriate technology/Alternative Materials

Category D: Workshop/Model making/Architectural Design

DISCUSSION

After analysing the data on the architecture schools and curriculum it is understood that there are 421 active architecture schools in India admitting between 22000 to 23000 students into architecture course each year. Average number of courses offered in B.Arch. program during 5 years of study is 81.54 and average total course credit points for the entire program are 259.06. Maximum number of courses in any school with syllabus containing topics on Bamboo for construction are 4 (four). 131 schools out of 355 do not have any course with syllabus containing topic on Bamboo construction. 149 schools out of 355 merely have 1 subject containing a topic on Bamboo construction in its syllabus. Only 75 schools have 2

to 4 courses containing topics on Bamboo construction. On an average each course of B.Arch. program has 3.18 credits and the credit associated with topics on Bamboo works out to be just 0.30. Only three schools out of 355 schools offers an independent course of 2 or 3 credits on Bamboo construction at 4th or 6th semester level.

A critical study of “The guidelines for the courses and periods of studies” provided in Appendix-A, page 29 to 31 of Minimum Standards of Architecture education 2020 of Council of Architecture shows that there is no single direct reference to “Bamboo” in this guiding document although this forms the basis for the formulation of the curriculum of B.Arch. programme and the syllabus of the subjects in the curriculum of educational institutions in India.

The syllabi of all the 355 colleges contain extensive teaching modules on Concrete, Steel, Timber and Bricks in the subjects spread over I to VIII semesters with an average credits of 40 assigned to these topics as against 0.30 credits assigned to the topic of Bamboo.

INFERENCE

Outcome of the analysis and further discussion on the analysis indicates that the Bamboo does not find a good place as mainstream construction material in the academic curriculum of architecture schools in India. It is very much visible from very low credits (0.30) assigned to Bamboo topics in the curriculum of architecture. The topic of Bamboo as a potential sustainable material for construction appears to be grossly neglected and is dealt in a very superficial manner in most of the schools. Required exercises and assignments on Bamboo construction are not listed in any of the curriculum. The course outcomes are very generic in nature and rarely do they relate to Bamboo directly.

A mandatory syllabus with necessary contents on Bamboo construction and greater number of credits for the topics on Bamboo construction are needed in the curriculum to enhance the intensity of learning Bamboo technology. Independent subject on construction techniques using Bamboo or subjects combined with topics on other materials could be spread over few semesters to bring a greater focus on the topic. Mandatory design exercises integrating Bamboo technology could also be included in syllabi of mid and higher level semesters to develop competence in designing and detailing the Bamboo structures.

To further enhance the awareness and competence an independent Bamboo technology laboratory and workshop can be recommended that will facilitate to gain hands on experience and innovations in Bamboo construction. Indian text books and authentic technical literature on Bamboo need to be developed. There is an immense need for publications on standard joinery details and well documented methods of construction using Bamboo. If the technical literature or text books are made easily accessible to institutes and students it will provide reliable knowledge support in this domain.

The number of students graduating and getting registered as Architect each year is voluminous (approved intake each year is 22984). If this large number of budding architects are equipped and galvanised appropriately for the use of Bamboo it would turn into a great advantage in favour of Bamboo. These architects themselves would become Bamboo ambassadors of the future. A model curriculum on Bamboo construction provided here can ensure to attain required competence on the usage of Bamboo in construction effectively.

Model curriculum on Bamboo Construction

This syllabus on Bamboo construction could be offered under one single subject at higher semesters or it can be split into three parts and merged with the courses on building construction/materials, Structural design and Workshop practices. Contents were formed considering the learning outcomes as mentioned below.

Course Outcome

CO1: Identify “Bamboo” as a material and different varieties, benefits of using.

CO2: Appreciate the bamboo as construction material, properties and usage in buildings.

CO3: Integrate and apply methods of construction using bamboo.

Module 1

Bamboo as a natural material, types and suitability for construction, available species in India, physical and structural properties, dimensional thumb rules for structural elements.

Module 2

Treatment of Bamboo to increase resistance and durability. Storing and stacking of Bamboo poles. Tools and techniques of cutting, splitting and slicing of Bamboo.

Module 3

Various types of joints and their suitability for specific condition. Hardware, fixtures and fastening used for joining Bamboo poles at different angles.

Module 4

Types of foundation for Bamboo columns, types and techniques of construction of composite Bamboo columns, Techniques of construction of Bamboo frame.

Module 5

Types and techniques of construction of Bamboo trusses, Bamboo space frames and Bamboo roofing.

Module 6

Bamboo walling and flooring methods, Bamboo doors and windows, Joinery used for the same.

Module 7

Structural design of Bamboo Columns, Bamboo Flooring, Bamboo Beams and Bamboo Trusses

Module 8

Integration of Bamboo with other materials of construction for best results in terms of form, function, performance and sustainability.

Module 9

Case study and documentation of Bamboo usage in contemporary and vernacular examples. Design exercise requiring the application of the techniques learnt to construct a structure of suitable magnitude using Bamboo as a main material.

REFERENCES

Department of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare. (2019). National Bamboo Mission revised guidelines 2019 Government of India Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare

United Nations Environment Programme (2021). 2021 Global Status Report for Buildings and Construction: Towards a Zero-emission, Efficient and Resilient Buildings and Construction Sector. Nairobi

Development Alternatives (2014). Bamboo: Green Construction Material in India. Retrieved from https://www.devalt.org/images/L2_ProjectPdfs/Resource_Efficiency_Publications_Catalogue_DA.pdf

Council of Architecture India. (n.d.). List of approved institutions. Council of Architecture, Ministry of Education, Government of India. Retrieved March 20, 2022, from <https://www.coa.gov.in/institutionStatus.php>

Council of Architecture. (n.d.). Minimum Standards of Architectural Education, Regulation 2020. Council of Architecture, Ministry of Education, Government of India. Retrieved March 20, 2022 from <https://www.coa.gov.in/showfile.php?lang=1&level=1&&sublinkid=1003&lid=599>

Mayring, Philipp : Qualitative content analysis: theoretical foundation, basic procedures and software solution. Klagenfurt, 2014. Retrieved May 24, 2022 from <http://nbn-resolving.de/urn:nbn:de:0168-ssoar-395173>

Gitam School of Architecture. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 21, 2022 from <https://vspgsa.gitam.edu/syllabus>

School of Planning and Architecture Vijaywada India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 29, 2022 from https://www.spav.ac.in/pdf/B.Arch-Credit_Pattern_Syllabus.pdf

Chandigarh College of Architecture Chandigarh India (n.d.). .B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 08, 2022 from <http://103.120.30.150:8084/Uploads/637647953761124248.pdf>

School of Planning and Architecture New Delhi India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 08, 2022 from <http://spa.ac.in/writereaddata/Arch%20Syllabus%20New.pdf>

MS University Baroda India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 13, 2022 from <https://www.msubaroda.ac.in/asset/storage/files/New%20Syllabus.pdf>

Sarvajanik University Surat India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 13, 2022 from <https://scetarch.ac.in/Downloads.aspx>

Saurashtra University Rajkot India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 13, 2022 from <https://scetarch.ac.in/Downloads.aspx>

Charutar Vidya Mandal University Vallabh Vidyanagar India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 13, 2022 from <http://smaid.edu.in/content/2020/Syllabus/21/11.pdf>

Sardar Patel University. (n.d.) B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 20, 2022 from https://cloud.spuvvn.edu/wp-content/uploads/Syllabi_data/b_arch/Detail%20Syllabus%20Bachelor%20of%20Architecture%20New.pdf

NIT Hamirpur Hamirpur India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 20, 2022 from https://nith.ac.in/wp-content/uploads/2016/12/Architecture_syllabus.pdf

Pandit Lakhmichand State University of Performing and Visual Arts Rohatak India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 21, 2022 from <https://plcupva.ac.in/sylabiipua/>
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1dciAtOXeC17sAWg1U93MIEOXFJh3JKrP/view>

Birla Institute of Technology Mesra Ranchi India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 06, 2022 from https://www.bitmesra.ac.in/UploadedDocuments/adminarch/files/FULL_Syllabus_Structure_ARCH_27_11_2019.pdf

Vir Narmad South Gujrat University Surat India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 20, 2022 from <https://www.vnsgu.ac.in/departments/architecture/courses/Final%20B.Arch.pdf>

Navrachana University Vadodara India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 20, 2022 from https://nuv.ac.in/pdf/Seda/BArch_Curriculum.pdf

University of Jammu Jammu India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 21, 2022 from https://www.jammuuniversity.ac.in/sites/default/files/inline-files/BArch_18_19_20.pdf

Manipal Academy of Higher Education Manipal India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 19, 2022 from <https://manipal.edu/content/dam/manipal/mu/foa/document/6.%20B.Arch%20Course%20Contents.pdf>

Visvesvaraya Technological University Belagavi India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 15, 2022 from <https://bmssa.ac.in/files/VTU2009/B.Arch%20syllabus%202018.pdf>

NITTE Institute of Architecture Mangalore India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 19, 2022 from https://drive.google.com/file/d/1KMDzGizK99wOJNS_tYQoFVCHCZoVEDUd/view

Reva University Bangalore India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 19, 2022 from <https://revaeduin.s3.ap-south-1.amazonaws.com/uploads/images/1644845960.pdf>

Christ University Bangalore India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 19, 2022 from <https://christuniversity.in/faculty-of-engineering/school-of-architecture/school-of-architecture/syllabus/416/2019>

APJ Abdul Kalam Technological University Thiruvananthapuram India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 19, 2022 from [file:///C:/Users/user1/Downloads/B.Archcurriculum\(1-10semesters\)asonJan2019.pdf](file:///C:/Users/user1/Downloads/B.Archcurriculum(1-10semesters)asonJan2019.pdf)

Cochin University of Science and Technology Kochi India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 21, 2022 from https://www.mcap.edu.in/uploadFiles/downloads//CUSAT_SYLLABUS-2021_Scheme1641895301.pdf

University of Calicut Calicut India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 21, 2022 from <https://www.mescoa.com/brochures/B.ArchprogrammeSyllabus2017.pdf>

Mumbai University Mumbai India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 23, 2022 from <http://www.sirjjarchitecture.org/syllabus.html>

Visvesvaraya National Institute of Technology Nagpur India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved February 13, 2022 from http://vnit.ac.in/arch/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/B_Arch_VNIT_Overall_Syllabus_I_X_Sem_Final_March2018-1.pdf

Cochin University of Science and Technology Kochi India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 21, 2022 from https://www.mcap.edu.in/uploadFiles/downloads//CUSAT_SYLLABUS-2021_Scheme1641895301.pdf

Mahatma Gandhi University Kottayam India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 21, 2022 from <https://www.mgu.ac.in/inc/uploads/2020/04/B-Arch-Syllabus.pdf>

Shivaji University Kolhapur India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 21, 2022 from <http://www.unishivaji.ac.in/uploads/syllabus/Engineering%20&%20Technology/Syllabus%202019-20/B.%20Arch.%20Part%20I%202019.PDF>

Dr Babasaheb Ambedkar Technological University Lonere India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 23, 2022 from <https://dbatu.ac.in/revised-syllabus-b-arch-2019-20/>

Rashtrasant Tukadoji Maharaj Nagpur University Nagpur India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 21, 2022 from https://www.nagpuruniversity.ac.in/links/Syllabus/UG/Faculty_of_Science/BArch_Scheme_of_Examination_27012021.pdf

Maulana Azad National Institute of Technology Bhopal India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 21, 2022 from <http://www.manit.ac.in/sites/default/files/documents/050820B.Arch%20program%20detailed%20syllabus%20July%202020%20FINAL.pdf>

School of Planning & Architecture Bhopal India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 23, 2022 from <http://spabhopal.ac.in/Syllabus.aspx>

Sri Sri University Cuttak India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 27, 2022 from <https://srisriuniversity.edu.in/wp-content/uploads/2017/09/Faculty-of-Architerture-B.Arch-Syllabus-2020.pdf>

Vir Surendra Sai University of Technology Sambalpur India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 24, 2022 from <https://vssut.ac.in/documents/Architecture-19-20.pdf>

Guru Nanak Dev University Amritsar India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 24, 2022 from <http://gndu.ac.in/syllabus/201617/PHYPLN/BACHELOR%20OF%20ARCHITECTURE%20SEMESTER%20I%20TO%20X.pdf>

Maharaja RanjitSingh Punjab Technical University Bathinda India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 24, 2022 from [https://www.mrsptu.ac.in/uploads/daa_notices/syllabus/march_17/MRSPTU%20B.Tech%20Architecture%20Syllabus%20\(Sem%201-10\)%202016%20Batch%20onwards%20updated%20on%2017.3.2017.pdf](https://www.mrsptu.ac.in/uploads/daa_notices/syllabus/march_17/MRSPTU%20B.Tech%20Architecture%20Syllabus%20(Sem%201-10)%202016%20Batch%20onwards%20updated%20on%2017.3.2017.pdf)

I K Gujral Punja Technical University Jalandhar India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 24, 2022 from https://pitk.ptu.ac.in/userfiles/file/syllabus/engg/23-11-2015%20B_Arch_for%20Updation_20-11-15.pdf

Pondicherry University Pondicherry India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 24, 2022 from https://backup.pondiuni.edu.in/sites/default/files/downloads/B.Arch_%20syllabus%202017-18%20onwards-18092019.pdf

Malaviya National Institute of Technology Jaipur India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 24, 2022 from https://mnit.ac.in/dept_arch/downloads/Syllabus/UG/BArch_Syllabus.pdf

Rajasthan Technical University Kota India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 24, 2022 from <https://rtu.ac.in/home/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/Scheme%20%20I%20to%20X%20Sem%20%20&%20%20Syllabus%20I%20to%20VI%20Sem.%20%20for%202014-15%20and%20onwords-04%20Apr%202017.pdf>

Poornima University Jaipur India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 24, 2022 from <https://www.poornima.edu.in/schemes-syllabus/current-schemes-syllabus/>

Vivekananda Global University Jaipur India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 24, 2022 from <https://vgu.ac.in/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/2019-2020-3.pdf>

Anna University Chennai India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 20, 2022 from <https://midas.ac.in/B.-Arch.-I-X.pdf>

National Institute of Technology Tiruchirapalli India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 24, 2022 from <https://www.nitt.edu/home/academics/curriculum/B.Arch-2019.pdf>

SRM Institute of Science and Technology Kattankulathur India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 24, 2022 from https://drive.google.com/file/d/1_NEoI2CUSdf8fIoIM_iYkxwCxU9GJMs9/view

Bharath Institute of Higher Education and Research Chennai India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 24, 2022 from https://www.bharathuniv.ac.in/nirf/archtech/Regulation/BARCH_R2018.pdf

Hindustan Institute of Technology and Science Chennai India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 20, 2022 from <https://hindustanuniv.ac.in/assets/pdf/ug/CBCS/B.Arch-Curriculum-Syllabus18-19.pdf>

Periyar Maniaamai Institute of Science and Technology Thanjavur India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 24, 2022 from <https://www.pmu.edu/department-of-architecture/pdf/CURRICULUM%20&%20SYLLABUS%202018.pdf>

Karpagam Academy of Higher Education Coimbatore. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 24, 2022 from <https://kahedu.edu.in/n/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/B.Arch-Syllabus-2021-22.pdf>

Crescent Institute of Science and Technology Chennai India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 20, 2022 from <http://www.crescentschoolofarchitecture.com/pdf/B.Arch.pdf>

Vellore Institute of Technology Vellore India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 20, 2022 from <https://vit.ac.in/sites/default/files/B.Arch/B.Arch-Curriculum-Syllabus-2018.pdf>

Jawaharlal Nehru Architecture and Fine Arts University Hyderabad India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 20, 2022 from https://www.jnafau.ac.in/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/Syllabus_New.pdf

Deenbandhu Chhotu Ram University of Science and Technology, Murthal India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 20, 2022 from http://www.dcrustm.ac.in/wp-content/uploads/2014/08/BArch_Ordinance_SchemeB_Syllabus_I_X-2.pdf

Mysore University Mysore India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 19, 2022 from <https://uni-mysore.ac.in/sites/default/files/content/b.arch-2019.pdf>

Biju Patnaik University of Technology Cuttack India. (n.d.). B.Arch. Curriculum. Retrieved March 29, 2022 from <http://www.bput.ac.in/documents/admindocs/B.Arch-Merge-14-09-2017.pdf>

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author declares that he has no conflict of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the author upon reasonable request.